

INFLUENCE OF FIBRE ARCHITECTURE ON IMPACT AND FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF FLAX FIBRE-BASED COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

In recent years, the fiber reinforced composite industry has grown exponentially in many areas such as automotive, aerospace and construction. Lately, the use of natural fibers as replacement of less environmentally-friendly products, such as glass fibers, has become a strong interest in the composite industry, in response to society's demand for more renewable resources. In this context, the use of flax fibre is increasing thanks to key functionalities, such as acoustic and thermal insulation, vibration damping, as well as renewability. In terms of mechanical performance, flax fibers are known to be as stiff as glass fibers, and even stiffer than glass when normalised to their low density. Flax fibres are among the strongest of the natural fiber family.

As of today, a major lack of data on natural fibre durability properties, such as fatigue behaviour and impact resistance, has been limiting the use of these fibres for high performance applications. In the case of fatigue, few papers such as from Liang et al. [1] relate to this behaviour. They have shown an increase of the stiffness of a single flax fibre for a certain number of loading cycles which rose from 40 GPa up to 70 GPa, the first being very low compared to other studies. Similarly, Silva et al. [2] have shown for sisal fibres, that at fatigue stresses below 50% of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS), all tested fibres can resist more than 10^6 cycles as well as show a slight increase of the stiffness. As for the impact resistance, it is documented as the greatest threat to natural

composite structures. It was shown by Santulli [3] that fibre defects have a large role in the impact resistance of natural fibre composites because they decrease the fibre bridging effect that prevents further development of a crack, which may cause the fibres to bend and pull-out early from the polymer during the impact.

The aim of this work is to study the impact resistance and fatigue behaviour of flax fibre composites for various preform architectures. This investigation is crucial in order to assess the durability of the materials since these properties have a great influence on the service life, product safety and liability. This will be compared for thermoset (TS) and thermoplastic (TP) matrices. Resin transfer moulding (RTM) and compression moulding were used to manufacture the plates.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

A thermoset epoxy (Th) *Epikote 828LVEL* ($\eta \approx 10$ - 12 Pa.s), combined with a *Dytek DCH-99* hardener (15.2 phr), and thermoplastic (Tp) Maleic Anhydride grafted Polypropylene (PPMa) sheet were used as matrices. Table 1 regroups the data for the flax preforms architectures used in this study. Unidirectional fabrics are received commingled with PPMA and with epoxy sizing for the epoxy experiments.

Table 1: Flax fibres characteristics.

Flax fibre preform architectures	Areal density ρ_{sur} (g/m ²)	1 ply thickness (mm)	Twist angle ($^{\circ}$)	Crimp warp/weft (%)	Acronym	Supplier
Mat	300	0,21	-	0/0	MA	Ecotechnilin
Plain weave	285	0,2	19-20	5,60/2,33	PW	Libeco
Twill 2x2	180	0,12	15	7,50/1,33	TW	Libeco
Twill 2x2 (low twist)	400	0,23	≈ 3	2,40/2	NT	Composite Evolution
Quasi-UD	300	0,21	20	0,4/0	Q-UD	B-Comp
UD	122	0,08	0	0/0	UD	Procotex

2.2 Composite manufacturing and Testing

2.2.1 Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM)

Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) processes are widely used to manufacture composite parts for various industries such as wind energy and automotive. An appropriate selection of the materials and proper optimization of the manufacturing parameters are keys to produce parts with improved properties. However, the infusion processes are limited by the low viscosity required to impregnate the fibrous reinforcement and the permeability [4]. In LCM processes, the impregnation of the fibrous preform and time required to fill-up the mould are intimately related to the injection and vacuum pressure as well as the viscosity of the resin. Flax fibres are less permeable to the resin due to the very dense nature once compacted and hollow structure which is the cause of slow fibre impregnation and also may create voids inside the laminate. In that case, the resin speed is controlled by the pressure gradient inside the mould.

The fibres were placed between the two rigid steel mould parts and were clamped together with an hydraulic press. The advantage of this process is that the thickness of the laminates is well controlled by the mould cavity as well as obtaining high surface quality on both surfaces. A spacer was added to adjust the depth of the cavity in order to

obtain the same thickness of $2\text{mm} \pm 0.05\text{mm}$. The fibres were manufactured using the same experimental parameters, $P_{inlet}=1\text{bar}$, $P_{vacuum}=1\text{bar}$ (see Fig. 1). Post-pressure of 3 bars. The RTM set up was heated up to 40°C in order to reduce the viscosity of the resin and improve impregnation of the fibres. The temperature was then increased to 70°C for 1h after the injection to cure the part. Later on, the plates were de-moulded and post-cured at 150°C for 1h.

Fig. 1 : Schematic side view RTM manufacturing process [5].

2.2.2 Compression Moulding (CM)

Thermoplastic composites were prepared by compression moulding using stacking of 3 to 7 flax

preform layers, each consisting of untreated fibres sandwiched between PPMA thermoplastic films. To obtain good impregnation, the temperature used was about 20°C higher than the melting temperature of the polymer and a pressure of 40 bars was used for consolidation. In all cases, the natural fibres and films were dried at least eight hours at 60°C to prevent problems due to moisture. A 2 mm spacer was used to set the fibre volume fraction of approximately 40% by weight measurements.

2.2.3 Composites lay-up

To manufacture the flax composites previously presented, lay-up of several flax preforms in layers was done. For Mats and weaves, preforms were stacked in warp direction. As for UD and Quasi-UDs made of continuous fibres, they are produced with balanced and symmetric cross-ply in the (0, 90)_s directions detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Composite Lay-up for all fabrics considered.

Flax fibre preform architectures	Lay-up
MA	(0) ₃
PW	(0) ₄
TW	(0) ₇
NT (low twist)	(0) ₄
Q-UD	(0,90) _s
UDTp	(0, 90) ₂ 0 (90,0) ₂
UDTh	(0,90) _{3s}

2.3 Tensile, fatigue and impact testing

Tensile and flexural mechanical tests were performed using an Instron testing machine #4505 and #4467 respectively, in the longitudinal direction of the samples. For the flexural properties, samples of 2x10x100 mm were tested using a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min; a load cell

of 5 kN and a span length of 64 mm were used according to ASTM D790 standard. For the tensile tests, samples of 2x25x250 mm were tested using a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min; a load cell of 100 kN and a gauge length of 150 mm were used according to ASTM D3039 standard. Also, the displacement was measured with a 50 mm extensometer. A minimum of 5 samples were tested to ensure reproducibility and reliable standard deviations. The tensile modulus has been calculated between 0.1 and 0.3% deformation. Fatigue testing was investigated using ASTM D3479 as the standard. Tension-tension fatigue tests with a loading ratio of $R = 0.1$, a loading frequency (f) of 5 Hz and a loading level (S/S_0) range from 0.3 to 0.9 UTS, were conducted at 22°C (room temperature). Samples were prepared with the same dimensions according to the ASTM D3039 for static tensile testing. The test is set to stop if the samples do not fail after 10E7 cycles, referred as N_{max} .

As for the impact resistance investigation, two aspects were assessed, damage resistance, and absorbed energy. Damage resistance is the resistance till first damage and focuses on the damage after an impact event, whereas the absorbed energy quantifies the amount of energy uptake during a full penetration impact event. A third aspect of impact is damage tolerance, the ability to sustain defects safely until repair can be effected; this will be investigated later on. The absorbed energy and the damage resistance are measured according to ISO 6603. To test damage resistance, the ISO 6603 standard was adapted for non-perforation. All samples had dimensions of 2x100x100mm.

It has to be noted that the fibre volume fraction V_f plays a key role to obtain high mechanical properties which are also dependant on the length of fibers. In order to standardize results from all samples, a V_f of 40% was used to calculate the number of layers necessary to obtain a laminate thickness of 2mm. Only the mat preforms were consolidated at $V_f = 30\%$ due to their bulky nature. A fibre density of 1.45g/cm³ (ρ_{vol}) is considered for the calculations of the fibre volume fraction V_f using the following Equation 1:

$$Vf = \frac{\rho_{surf} * N}{\rho_{vol} * h} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where ρ_{surf} is the aerial density (gsm) and ρ_{vol} is the density of the fibers, N is the number of layers used and e is the composite laminate thickness.

2.4 Optical and Scanning Electron Microscopy

Optical microscopy allows the observation of the small details and defects of a composite sample. This technique is usually used for initial examination and characterization of the internal surface and qualitative assessment of the impregnation. This step is essential to confirm the mechanical properties results prior to proceeding to more detailed investigations such as impact or fatigue testing.

Fig. 2: Microscopy of the TW/ Epoxy plate: a) 500µm, b) 200µm scalebar.

The flax-based plate shown in Fig. 2a seems to have no apparent discontinuities and good adhesion. On millimetre level only very small porosities are detected (Fig. 2b). It has to be noted that these small spots may also be caused by a deficient interfacial adhesion between the fibres and the matrix as well as capillary or viscous forces. On micro level three other types of defects can be seen, as observed by SEM. Un-impregnated zones, micro cracks and bubbles are seen, as displayed in Fig. 3. The first defect is highly likely to occur in impregnating flax fibres. The flax yarn itself is composed of several technical fibres of 50-100 micron [6] in diameter and it is not easy for the resin to disperse around all of them.

The micro-cracks (between 1-5µm) shown in fig. 3 b) were only observed in thermoset matrix systems and have not been reported yet in literature. Their origin is hypothetically coming from the high vacuum of the SEM or it is intrinsic to the fibre type, since not all the fibre architectures were sensitive to it. The third defect shown, the bubbles were only seen in the thermoplastic systems, again not for all architectures. Here it could be related to the density of the weave; weaves with a higher areal density were more prone to it. It should be stated that even with the presence of these defects, the tensile test results were in agreement with literature and no serious influence can be assigned to them [7].

a) Unimpregnated zones

b) Micro cracks

c) Micro-bubbles

Fig. 3: Micro-defects present in the flax composites

Fig. 4: Longitudinal tensile stiffness and strength of flax fibre-based composites at $V_f = 40\%$.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of the tensile properties

The first step of understanding the effect of fibre architecture on fatigue and impact properties is to assess the quasi-static tensile and flexural results. Quasi-static tensile tests were carried out to obtain the stiffness (E) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of flax/epoxy and flax/PPMA composites. The results for E modulus and UTS are presented in Fig. 4 for thermoplastic and thermoset composites and these results are consistent with the literature [1, 6]. The efficiency of the composite usually depends on the length/diameter ratio of the fibres, which explains the variations in properties between the architectures, and their compatibility to the polymeric components,.

As expected, the values for the random mats (MA), at $V_f = 30\%$ are low which is likely caused by the fact that there is no preferential direction of the short fibres. The best case scenario for mat-based composites, would be to have fibres that are long enough to obtain a pseudo-continuous fibrous reinforcement.

The difference in properties for the different fibre architectures is better shown by the strength results. The variability in properties for the flax fabrics can be attributed to the fibre characteristics (e.g. extracting conditions, etc) and to the composite characteristics such as variable V_f . As to the effect of fibre architecture, the effect of fabric crimp, defined as the waviness of the yarn becomes apparent in Fig. 4. The tensile strength properties obtained for QUD and UD (0,90)s lay-ups, are typically higher than for the weaves, which is expected because for the UD's the effect of crimp is practically non-existent. The expected positive effect of low fibre twist in the twill fabrics, was not observed. The same tendencies are observed for either epoxy or PPMA matrices.

As for the strain to failure of the tested materials, the use of flax fibre weaves shows higher elongation at break than typically found for glass fibre weaves ($\approx 1.5\%$). The UD fabrics have a strain to failure of $\approx 1.75\%$, which is in the range or above the expected value (1.5%) for these samples [6]. In the literature, several authors reveal that, in tensile testing, the fibre architecture has an important effect on the strain to failure, which can be reduced by 60% once the fibres are processed into multi-axial or woven fabrics. This means, that the fabric crimp may have a sizable effect on the final properties of the laminates [8, 9].

3.2 Fatigue life assessment

Tensile-tensile fatigue cycling was carried out at load levels corresponding to various fractions of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) registered during quasi-static testing. This value is referred to as S_0 , and is later used to normalise the load levels (S/S_0) that the sample will be subjected to.

The normalised stress/number of cycles to failure ($S-N$) curves, seen in Fig. 5a, show lower fatigue endurance for the flax specimens MA and PW than for glass samples. On the other hand, flax samples have a better fatigue endurance at normalised stress than comparable glass samples, in the studied life range going from $N=0$ to $N=N_{max}$. Results showed that at comparable normalised stresses, MAT flax composites had a comparable life as PW glass composites, obtained by Hussain et al.[10], and can resist more than 1×10^6 cycles at 0.3 normalised load level (see Fig. 5b). As well, flax PW has an enhanced fatigue performance compared to glass PW with the first being able to sustain around 100 000 cycles and the second only 20 000 cycles at a 0.65 load level. These results may help widen the application domain of flax fibre composites in replacing glass fibre by flax fibre.

Fig. 5 a) S/N Diagram of flax composite compared to glass composite; b) Normalised S/N diagram of flax composite compared to glass [10].

3.3 Impact resistance

Low velocity impact typically occurs at velocities below 10m/s. At this speed the whole structure will respond and there will be more elastic absorption. This kind of impact response is also referred to as quasi static. Applications for flax composites are believed to lie mainly in this area. In this study the impact resistance is characterised via a drop weight impact test, which is preferred above Izod or Charpy, because of the more realistic loading case.

3.3.1 Perforation behaviour

Drop weight low velocity impact tests till perforation were performed, in order to assess the absorbed energy behaviour of flax composites. Each time eight specimens were prepared except for the UDTp only four, due to limited material. The weight of the impactor was 3.170kg with a striker top diameter of 20mm and a clamping ring of 40mm. The drop height for all thermoplastic samples was 0.6m and for all thermoset samples 0.4m. This energy was chosen to reach perforation for all samples. This leads to an incident energy for the thermoplastic and thermoset samples of respectively 12.4J and 18.7J. Force and displacement were recorded to determine the absorbed energy via two methods; the velocity method and the force-integration method (see Fig. 6). Both calculation methods are taken into account in order to assess the relationship between absorbed energy and fibre architecture.

Fig. 6: Absorbed energy after Perforation impact: Velocity method vs Force-Displacement method according to ASTM D7136 And ISO 6603 standards.

Literature suggests that the absorbed energy for full penetration depends strongly on the fibre volume fraction; fibre architecture and matrix are mentioned as secondary factors [11]. During perforation the major forms of energy absorption are fibre shear out, delamination and elastic flexure.

Fig. 7 displays the absorbed energy for perforation for the different architectures and matrices considered. To have a fair comparison, the absorbed energy was normalised to the total amount of fibre, defined as the volume fraction*thickness ($V_f \times t$) of the specimen. This has proven its efficiency as shown by Caprino et al. [12] and Bibo et al.[11]. Only the mat was not normalised via this method since 30Vf% is the highest volume fraction attainable with this architecture.

As seen in Fig.7, the perforation energy for a plain woven (PW) architecture, calculated using the velocity (grey) or the integral method (light grey), shows a significantly better performance for the thermoplastic matrix (PPMA) than in case of the thermoset matrix (epoxy); the increase in absorbed energy is more than 50%. The same performance for thermoplastic matrices can be seen for both twill (TW, NT) materials and the UD. The effect is less pronounced for the Quasi-UD (QU) and not seen for the mat (MA). It can be stated that in the flax composites tested, the matrix does have a non-negligible influence on the absorbed energy; this differs from the results found for glass fibre composites by Schrauwen et al. [13] where no clear effect of matrix ductility could be observed. Flax fibre composites are characterised by lower perforation energies than glass fibre composites which can bring the contribution of the matrix ductility to the total absorbed energy, more to the front.

Looking at the two calculation methods it can be seen that the velocity method typically gives lower values than the force-displacement method. Also the variation on the velocity method's mean is usually higher than the force-displacement method. From this it is concluded that the force-displacement method is a better way of comparing

the different energies measured. In the velocity method, the time gage for calculation of the velocity after impact needs to be selected by the operator, which is rather arbitrary and explains the big scatter on the measurements.

A hypothesis test was performed for the thermoset and thermoplastic samples with as null hypothesis, the equality of all means for different fibre architectures. The alternative hypothesis being that at least one of the means differs. With an α value of 0.05 we were able to reject the null hypothesis and state that the means differ and thus the fibre architecture has an influence on the perforation energy. However having a closer look at the graphs in Fig. 7 for the thermoset samples, it can be seen that the QU performs higher and for the thermoplastic samples that the MA and the NT perform lower. Eliminating these means from the hypothesis test, the null hypothesis could not be rejected anymore. Though caution should be taken

interpreting this result, since not rejecting the null hypotheses does not mean that the means are indeed equal, there is only not enough evidence to prove that they are not. The lower value for the thermoplastic mat material can be due to the contribution of two parameters. First of all the lower fibre volume fraction, for which the effect seems less pronounced in combination with the thermoset matrix and secondly the quality of the sample. Both the mat and the twill (with low twist) have very high areal densities and showed difficulties to produce a defect free composite. Small air bubbles were present throughout the samples which were not able to escape during the compression moulding process, as shown in Fig. 3c.

Fig. 7: Total absorbed energy of 2mm thick samples for different fibre architectures; first column by the velocity method, second column by force integration. Normalised to equal Vf*, except for the mat where Vf = 30%

3.3.2 Non-perforation performance

Non-perforating drop weight low velocity impact tests were performed in order to assess a second type of impact behaviour, namely damage resistance. The same impactor configuration was used (weight = 3.170kg and striker diameter 20mm). The clamping ring was enlarged to 80mm to be sure the delaminated zone would not be restricted by it. A rebound mechanism was put in place so that only one strike per specimen occurred. With a drop height of 0.1m, the incident energy on both thermoplastic and thermoset samples was 3.1J. The absorbed energy for thermoplastic and thermoset matrices is influenced by the kind of failure mechanism occurring. Thermoplastic samples are not so prone to matrix cracks and delaminations and prohibit fibre breakage more, whereas thermoset samples show more matrix cracks, delamination and fibre breakage for the same incident energy. For assessing the damage resistance, the main parameter to look at is the damaged area. In order to have a normalised comparison it is normalised by the absorbed energy. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows c-scan images of the different configurations. It can be seen that the damaged area for all thermoset systems is higher than for the thermoplastic systems; this is as expected since the thermoplastic nature of the PPMA is more effective in hindering the damage to spread. For all woven fabrics (PW,TW,NT) and cross-plies (QU,UD) the damage was represented by a star shape, following the warp and weft or 0-90° directions of the fabric or plies. The non-woven mat either had three or four crack-lines not following any preferential direction.

Fig. 9 shows the absorbed energy per damaged area for the different architectures and matrices. For this graph the absorbed energy was not normalised to $V_f \cdot t$ since not such dependence for delamination in non-penetration impact tests was found in literature. However, all samples had similar thickness of 2 mm. All thermoplastic systems show higher results. The thermoset values vary between 20-40% of the corresponding thermoplastic system. As can be seen from **Error! Reference source not found.** the damaged area of

the twill (TW) and the Quasi UD (QU) are for the same incident energy, smaller in comparison with the other architectures. This results in a higher absorbed energy/ damaged area as seen in Fig. 9. This means that the twill and the quasi-UD that were investigated perform better than the other architectures on damage resistance.

Fig. 8 Damaged area of epoxy/flax composites and PPMA/flax composites before and after one impact event with an incident energy of 3.1J. Scanned area before = 100x100mm, after = 60x60mm.

Fig. 9: Absorbed impact energy per damaged area of non-perforated samples with initial impact of 3.1J; TP values should be read from the right axis.

Another indicator for the ability of a material to resist initial damage is the incipient damage load (P_i) as seen in Fig.10a) [14]. P_i reflects the damage initiation in the form of delamination. For some materials it can be seen as load drop before the maximum load is reached (P_m) and for others the

load drop becomes obscure and the point can only be identified by a change in slope. The P_i can be derived from a force-displacement curve, but here the force-time curve was used to facilitate the reading by avoiding the loop seen in the force-displacement curve due to rebound. Fig.10b) shows the incipient damage loads for the different fibre architectures. It can be seen that the highest loads are those of the quasi UD fibre architecture, both with the thermoplastic and thermoset matrix and the twill with the thermoplastic matrix. These are the same fabrics that attained the highest values for absorbed energy/damaged area. For this reason it can be confirmed that the P_i is a good indicator for the damage resistance of a material. The twill in a $(0)_7$ stack up and the QU in a $(0-90)_{2s}$ stack up attain both high force values before significant delamination failure or matrix cracking in the laminate occurs. It is believed that the high value of the ends count and the picks count, also related with the fineness of the yarn, can play an important role in this. A thinner fibre yarn typically has a larger strain to failure which can be linked to the twist angle of the yarns. because the fibre tends [15] and can absorb more energy before inducing defects, leading to a higher P_i . On the other hand more ends per count due to a finer yarn lead to more obstacles for the progressing damage and thus to lower damaged area and higher absorbed energy/damaged area.

a)

b)

Fig. 10 a) Force-Time curve for a TWTh sample. P_i = incipient damage load, P_m = maximum load, b) Incipient load for the different fibre architectures derived from the Force-Time curve for the non-perforating tests.

4 Conclusions

Tensile, fatigue and impact tests were carried out in order to assess the long term behaviour of flax-based composites. Mechanical property evaluations showed higher tensile properties for epoxies compared to PPMA samples, which was expected. TW, PW and UD combined with epoxies were found to have the best performance. For samples comingled with PPMA, Quasi-UD and UD were the best ones. It was observed that at normalised stress, the fatigue life of flax/epoxy PW composite is higher than in case of glass PW composite, which validates the possibility of replacing glass fibre by flax in the near future for certain applications.

The absorbed energy in perforation tests brought the influence of matrix ductility to the front, this in contradiction to research performed on glass fibres. Thermoplastic composites were able to absorb more energy than their thermoset counterparts. However, for the same type of resin no clear conclusion about the influence of fibre architecture could be drawn. The damage resistance tested by non-perforation tests also revealed the influence of the matrix ductility. Thermoplastic composites

showed higher absorbed energy/damaged area values and higher incipient damage loads P_i . For damage resistance, a clear influence of fibre architecture could be identified, with the quasi-UD and twill fabric outperforming the others. As explanation the high ends count, picks count and the fineness of the yarns are suggested. In this study no clear distinction between woven fabrics and cross ply laminates could be made, as was clearly seen in previous studies. Future work will be directed to a better understanding of the composites' performance after impact as well as working on increasing the fibre/matrix interface bonding, which may increase the mechanical and fatigue properties.

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